

scores and were resistant to BPH, but IR36, ASD7, and Babawee had higher scores in some years.

In the biotype test of Guangdong (Table 2), most of the scores for IR26 were more than 7 across the different locations and years, with some not significantly different from those of TN1. Mudgo scores ranged from 4.0 to 8.8, showing its tendency to be

susceptible. TR36 and ASD7 scores were higher than those of PTB33. The two varieties were particularly damaged by BPH populations in Xinhui in 1994, Gaozhou in 1993, and Lechang in 1994. PTB33 was resistant to every BPH population.

The results indicate that the BPH biotype has been changing in Guangdong.

BPH biotype 1 dominated the population before 1989, but in recent years it seems that BPH biotype 2 dominates with BPH biotype 3 mixed into the population. Sources of resistance to these two BPH biotypes should be considered for use in BPH-resistance breeding. ■

Integrated pest management—others pests

Loss of harvested rice due to rodents in central India

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During Oct to Nov in much of central India, harvested rice is stacked up to 6 m high in circular (3-7.6 m diam) heaps on threshing floors. A threshing floor, which covers 0.1-0.5 ha, is prepared in the field by leveling the ground and then compressing and plastering it with cow dung; size depends on the number of farmers involved and on their holding sizes.

Rice often remains heaped for 2-3 mo before threshing because immediately after

the harvest, farmers are busy preparing their fields and sowing the next crop. Limited food and shelter in the harvested fields and disturbances during the preparation force most of the field rodents to move to other places. Some settle under the rice heaps, causing severe damage to the harvested rice. During threshing, they move to the new crops in the field.

We assessed the loss of harvested rice to rodents and their burrow patterns under heaps in five villages (see table) of central India. Five threshing floors were surveyed in each village; all were found to be infested with *Bandicota bengalensis* and *Millardia meltada meltada* with the former predominating. *B. bengalensis* constructed 1.2- to 3.9-m long labyrinth-like burrow systems under the heaps. The burrows were like

Burrows of *Bandicota bengalensis* Gray under rice heaps on threshing floor.

Loss to rodents of harvested rice on threshing floors. Central India.

Village	Threshing months	Heaps/ threshing floor (no.)	Burrows/ threshing floor ^a (no.)	Burrow dimension		Hoarded grain/ threshing floor (kg)	Rodent species
				Length (m)	Depth (cm)		
Amarpur	Jan-Feb	13	47 (3.6)	3.5	20.7	10.2 0.8 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Poudikhurd	Jan	11	29 (2.6)	1.2	15.5	4.8 0.4 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Tamoria	Dec-Jan	9	13 (1.4)	1.8	17.9	2.9 0.3 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Dhanpuri	Dec	11	15 (1.4)	2.6	19.3	1.6 0.2 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Sitasarovar	Jan-Feb	10	35 (3.5)	3.9	21.4	13.5 1.4 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i> <i>M. meltada</i>

^a Figures in parentheses are burrow densities/heap. ^b Hoarded grain/burrow.

open canals (see figure). Underground tunnels were rarely observed. The mean burrow depth varied from 15.5 to 21.4 cm; food chambers were located within. The burrow depths under rice heaps were less than those found in fields and along bunds.

The burrow density (no. of burrows ÷ no. of heaps) was the least (1.4) in Tamoria and Dhanpuri villages, where threshing was completed by early January. It was greatest (3.6) in Amarpur and Sitasarovar where threshing lasted into February. The burrow density increased as threshing was delayed. Hoarding loss due to rodents in early threshed areas was 1.6 kg grain/threshing floor and 13.4 kg grain/threshing floor in late threshed areas.

Farmers are advised to avoid late threshing to minimize the loss of harvested rice to rodents. ■